

Adoption of Open Educational Resources (OER) in Higher Education in Germany: An Explorative Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Keywords

Open Educational Resources, Open Education, Attitudes, Intention-Behaviour Gap

Purpose of this paper

Although the idea of openness has gained momentum in the educational discourse, the situation of the adoption of Open Educational Resources (OER) in education is still in a developmental stage (Bozkurt, Koseoglu, & Singh, 2019). Germany, in this regard, can be categorised as a laggard. This status is confirmed by the latest UNESCO report on understanding the impact of OER:

In Germany, OER adoption is also low, particularly outside the community of German OER experts in all sectors of education and training. For example, in higher education, there are no guidelines/recommendations or national portals for knowledge/OER exchange. OER are still considered as ‘not invented here’ by most educators. (UNESCO IITE, 2019, S. 27).

In addition to the lack of legal regulation and policy support (Neumann, Orr, & Muuß-Merholz, 2018; UNESCO IITE, 2019), another significant obstacle is that OER are not firmly entrenched in current educational practices. While the creation of OER repositories in higher education institutions is sprouting, there are hardly suitable and sustainable incentives for practitioners to adopt OER and use it in everyday teaching.

An initial step to spur the adoption of OER in Germany was the recent BMBF funding line OERinfo that funded 25 projects all over Germany (Surmann & Echterhoff, 2018). As one pivotal achievement OERinfo was established which, for the first time, serves as a central contact point for OER in Germany. OERinfo aims to bundle and disseminate information on the

subject in order to reach new target groups from all areas of education. Twenty-two projects aimed to qualify multipliers from the dominant educational sectors to create and use OER. The projects primarily intended to inform those who work in key positions in their respective educational fields and thus are able to convey the importance of the OER.

Notwithstanding the achievement of OERinfo to render the potentials of OER for a broader audience in education, the wider adoption and diffusion of OER in education is still limited. From a research perspective, particularly empirical research for the case of Germany has been weak so far.

The follow-up project of OERinfo (2018-2020) aims to narrow this research gap between theoretical assumptions and empirical findings. The research approach is based on the observed tension between the broad availability of OER (repositories) and its limited use in teaching.

Design/methodology/approach

Using a survey-based approach, it is planned to collect data about the status and barriers of OER across educational fields in Germany.

The underlying approach is twofold. First, it is intended to measure the attitudes of participants towards the practice of sharing and cooperation in general. Second, the specific attitudes towards OER are evaluated, and barriers to OER use are identified. Attitudes are conceptualised as describing a positive or negative evaluation of a person towards an object or event (Eagly & Chaiken, 1993). A definition widely accepted in the literature is that attitudes are objects comprising “anything a person may hold in mind, ranging from the mundane to the abstract, including things, people, groups, and ideas” (Bohner & Dickel, 2010, S. 392). Regarding the attitudes’ structure of a person, Rosenberg and Hovland (1960) have identified a taxonomy of responses which contains a cognitive (knowledge), an affective (feeling and emotions) and a behavioural (action) component.

The survey is distributed over two main channels. A broader audience is contacted using the communication channels of OERinfo and the four transfer partners (school, higher education, further education, vocational education). A more community-based approach is pursued by using specific events related to OER (OERcamp, conferences, workshops and training).

Findings/expected Findings

Although this is ongoing research, our preliminary sample suggests a paradox between a positive affective component towards OER but little practical usage (behavioural) which can best be explained by a classical intention-behaviour gap (Sheeran & Webb, 2016). Whereas the

attitudes of the majority of practitioners towards sharing in general and OER, in particular, are positive, the behavioural component reveals that OER are seldom actively used in educational practice.

As factors that could potentially explain the intention-behaviour gap, we plan to examine broader contextual factors that aggravate the adoption of OER, such as lack of time, legal uncertainties and institutional barriers etc. To determine these broader contextual influences, we use expert interviews and empirical data from the first funding periods of OERinfo.

Practical implications

Once we reconcile our results from the survey with the broader contextual factors, we expect to be able to render findings on how to lower the intention-behaviour gap. As our research is based on a design-based approach (Kerres & de Witt, 2011), we aim to develop concrete design recommendations from our findings of how to spur the adoption of OER in higher education.

What is original/value of paper

An empirical investigation of status and diffusion of OER in higher education. Develop concrete design recommendations on how to spur the adoption of OER.

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